

“INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION AND ITS IMPORTANCE”

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ABSTRACT

ICT is short for “Information and Communication Technologies.” It is similar to IT (Information Technology), but focuses more on telecommunications mediums, such as the Internet, cell phone networks, and satellite technology. Modern forms of ICT have made it possible for users across the world to communicate with each other in real-time on a regular basis. Examples include instant messaging, video-conferencing, online multiplayer gaming, and social networking websites. Modern information and communication technologies have created a “global village,” in which people can communicate with others across the world as if they were living next door. For this reason, ICT is often studied in the context of how modern communication technologies affect society.

Keywords- ICT, video-conferencing, Websites, Global village, Social networking.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years there has been a groundswell of interest in how computers and the Internet can best be harnessed to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of education at all levels and in both formal and non-formal settings. But ICTs are more than just these technologies; older technologies such as the telephone, radio and television, although now given less attention, have a longer and richer history as instructional tools. For instance, radio and television have for over forty years been used for open and distance learning, although print remains the cheapest, most accessible and therefore most dominant delivery mechanism in both developed and developing countries. The use of computers and the Internet is still in its infancy in developing countries, if these are used at all, due to limited infrastructure and the attendant high costs of access.

No one can deny the impact that technology continues to have on almost every aspect of our daily lives, nor the speed with which new developments are adopted by us. The mobile phone is ubiquitous, and not just for anytime anywhere voice communication. Broadband data connectivity brings access to the internet and our personal and business communications. GPS can give us geographical guidance. A camera gives us video as well as image and sound recording capability, and local storage continues to get ever larger and ever cheaper.

The world is becoming more and more competitive, and the quality of performance has become the key factor for school and personal program. Parents wish that their children climb the ladder of performance as high as possible. This desire for a high level of achievement shapes their attitude towards the educational system. In the present system, the concept of providing education is changed from only enhancing the achievement in subjects to harmonious development of learner.

now parents want that their kids get admission in that school which has facilities like smart classrooms, smart boards, computer based learning and hi-tech language laboratories.

It is necessary to use new tools and techniques in education. New tools and techniques are not only helpful for students but helpful for every human being. Using these tools and techniques students can do better not only in their study but can do in each and every sector. Among these tool and techniques ICT is most important tool. So "Thanks to ICT". Users can access information from all over the globe." Information and Communications Technologies (ICT) education is basically our society's efforts to teach its current and emerging citizens valuable knowledge and skills around computing and communications devices, software that operates them, applications that run on them and systems that are built with them.

ICT is complex and quickly changing, and it is confusing for many people. It is so pervasive in the modern world that everyone has some understanding of it, but those understandings are often wildly divergent.

There are many important dimensions to ICT education, including:

ICT/Digital Literacy – Today, everyone needs a basic understanding of ICT and how to make productive use of it, just to be good students, workers and citizens. Teaching people how to be competent basic users of ICT technologies is an important role of ICT education, so they will be successful in their academic and work careers, and so they can efficiently participate in modern technical society.

ICT Infrastructure and Support Applied Technologists – Beyond a basic user competency, our society also needs more knowledgeable and capable technical people to deploy manage and maintain ICT equipment, software and systems, so they work well for users. In all industries, these people manage computer and communications hardware, software and applications; networked systems; online information sharing, communication and commerce systems; business processes making use of these systems; and user support.

ICT Helps Teachers as well as students - The role of a teacher has changed now a day. A teacher will be able to integrate the use of ICT into his/her teaching effectively to develop various competencies like different types of skills as well as administrative and organizations skills. There are following ways that ICT can help teachers:

- It enables to enhance the initial preparation by giving good teaching training.
- It enables to give feedback.
- It enables to interact with students to understand their difficulties.
- It provides facility to access to different colleges, institutions and universities and experts centers.

Specialized Business and Industry Uses of ICT – As enabling technologies, ICT is used strategically in almost all businesses and industries. Many have developed specialized systems and uses of ICT, and many have specialized legal and regulatory requirements; quality control systems; integrations with production and research equipment and systems; security requirements; and software applications.

ICT Research and Development Scientists – ICT fields themselves are under constant pressure to evolve and improve. We need people who deeply understand the science and technologies underlying ICT and who can work to advance the fields.

Source: <https://nicetsurayya.wordpress.com>

Conclusion:

In virtually all modern businesses and industries and in modern society in general, ICT has key strategic roles. It is strategically important to develop citizens and workers who can competently and efficiently operate and add value in these systems and environments. ICT shall solve most of the issues related to quality and the latest demands of our society.

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